

To Study of Adjustment of Students in Ashram Schools and Private Schools

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Abstract:

The study was conducted to assess the adjustment of the students in ashram schools and Private Schools. The sample consisted of 100 students in ashram schools (50 boys & 50 Girls) and 100 students in private schools (50 boys & 50 Girls) were selected from Junnar Tehsil. The age of range of participants was between 14 to 16 years. Simple random sampling method for used for data collection. For this study adjustment inventory for school students (AISS) developed by A. K. P. Sinha & R. P. Singh (1993) was used to assess the adjustment of the selected respondent. Mean, SD, 't' value etc. statistics techniques were used for data analysis and interpreting. The findings were significant difference of overall adjustment and three areas in educational, social & emotional adjustment in ashram schools and private schools students. This means, the overall adjustment and educational, social and emotional adjustment of private schools students is higher than that of ashram schools students.

Introduction:

The adjustment is very simple and easy concept to understand. In school life, it is important to adapt to different types of friends, adjust to the curriculum, school, and education. If the students have good adjustment ability, they will have the ability to take initiative in any task, to have realistic objectives, to plan well, to try with restraint and to face successes and failures easily. Based on these qualities, students make good progress in school life. Paraneswarah & Beena (2004): "Adjustment is a process which a living organism acquires in a particular way of acting or behaving or changes an existing form of behavior or action." Adjustment is a process which goes on continuously in the life of a person from birth to death. A person has to do different types of adjustment in his life. It never happens that at particular time adjustment started and at particular time adjustment finished. A person has to do different types of adjustment for lifetime.

Ashram school:

Many government & private schools, colleges purpose is to teach, but the purpose behind it may be different. While inquiring about the government ashram school, it seems that these ashram school have emerged for the educational advancement of various tribes, girijans, vimukta tribes,

nomadic tribes and other adivasis, as it is not appropriate for some tribes to be deprived of education in the age of equal opportunity. Accommodation, meals and education of the above mentioned boys and girls are provided in these schools at the government expense. The educational, economic, social & family status of the students in ashram schools is backward. Lack of educational & other facilities, fear of students in schools, lack of attention from parents, helping the family by working at an early age are the reasons for high dropout rate among children. Due to these reasons, educational backwardness is seen in the students of ashram school. Is there an adjustment problem in these children to get that backwardness? This topic has been chosen for the purpose of getting the attention of the parents, society and teachers and for the progress of the children.

Private School:

Private schools students are found to be good financial, social and family status and are encouraged to study at home. There is a perception that education in private schools and teachers is to focus on how to ensure the overall development and progress of the children. Private schools are established by one or more individuals and controlled by the Board of Directors and the

Educational Officer. Starting the private school requires approval from the School committee. While giving this recognition, all the factors are taken in to consideration that the requirements of the school in the department (Area), Geographical Environment, number of students, other Government schools will not be affected. These schools receive funds from parents in the form of the donations and a few percent grant from the government.

Rationale of study:

Considering both the above schools, students and the environment, is really an adjustment problem for these students to get educational backwardness? This topic has been chosen for the purpose of getting the attention of the parents, society and teachers and for the progress of the children.

Objective of Study:

- 1) To study the adjustment of students in ashram schools and private schools.
- 2) To study the educational adjustment of students in ashram schools and private schools.
- 3) To study the social adjustment of students in ashram schools and private schools.
- 4) To study the emotional adjustment of students in ashram schools and private schools.

Hypothesis:

- 1) There is no significant difference in the adjustment of students in ashram schools and private schools.
- 2) There is no significant difference in the educational adjustment of students in

Result & Discussion:

Table No. 1 showing the significant difference in adjustment between students in ashram schools and private schools.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Adjustment	Ashram schools students	13.62	6.31	100	4.86	0.01
	Private schools students	9.78	4.64	100		

(A high score in the adjustment test indicates unsatisfactory adjustment, while a low score indicates excellent adjustment.)

The table no. 1 it is shows that, the ashram school students mean value is 13.62 and standard deviation value is 6.31. Like the private school students mean value is 9.78

ashram schools and private schools.

- 3) There is no significant difference in the social adjustment of students in ashram schools and private schools.
- 4) There is no significant difference in the educational adjustment of students in ashram schools and private schools.

Method:

1) Sample: In this study, researcher has select 100 students in ashram schools (50 boys & 50 Girls) and 100 students in private schools (50 boys & 50 Girls). Sample was select from Junnar Tehsil through simple random sampling method for used for data collection. The age of range of participants was between 14 to 16 years.

2) Variable: Independent Variable:- Ashram schools and private schools Students.

Dependent Variable:- Adjustment

3) Research Tools: Adjustment Inventory for School Students (AISS) - A. K. P. Sinha & R. P. Singh (1993) This test was designed for secondary school students between the ages of 14 to 18 years. This scale consists of 60 sentences, which are classified into three areas of adjustment: emotional, social, and educational. Out of these 60 statements, 20 statements are included in each field. Each statement has two options, 'Yes' & 'No'. The reliability of the test was found to be 0.93 by the test-retest method, while the validity of the test was found to be 0.51 which confirm the standardization of the scale.

4) Statistical Analysis:

In the present research Mean, SD, 't' value etc. Statistical techniques were used for the data analysis and interpretation.

be 4.86. This is significant at 0.01 levels. So the null hypothesis was rejected. That is, there was a significant difference of adjustment in ashram schools and private schools students.

Table No. 2 showing the significant difference in educational adjustment between students in ashram schools and private schools.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Educational Adjustment	Ashram schools students	3.72	2.48	100	3.52	0.01
	Private schools students	2.52	2.32	100		

(A high score in the adjustment test indicates unsatisfactory adjustment, while a low score indicates excellent adjustment.)

The table no. 2 it is shows that, the ashram schools students mean value is 3.72 and standard deviation value is 2.48. Like the private schools students mean value is 2.52 and standard deviation value is 2.32. The ashram schools students mean value is more than private schools students.

Obtained 't' value of the difference between the mean of these two groups was found to be 3.52. This is significant at 0.01 levels. So the null hypothesis was rejected. That is, there was a significant difference of educational adjustment in ashram schools and private schools students.

Table No. 3 showing the significant difference in social adjustment between students in ashram schools and private schools.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Social Adjustment	Ashram schools students	6.70	2.86	100	8.18	0.01
	Private schools students	4.90	2.00	100		

(A high score in the adjustment test indicates unsatisfactory adjustment, while a low score indicates excellent adjustment.)

The table no. 3 it is shows that, the ashram schools students mean value is 6.70 and standard deviation value is 2.86. Like the private schools students mean value is 4.90 and standard deviation value is 2.00. The ashram schools students mean value is more than private schools students. Obtained 't' value of the difference between the mean of these two groups was found to

be 8.18. This is significant at 0.01 levels. So the null hypothesis was rejected. That is, there was a significant difference of social adjustment in ashram schools and private schools students.

Table No. 4 showing the significant difference in emotional adjustment between students in ashram schools and private schools.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Emotional Adjustment	Ashram schools students	3.38	2.52	100	3.75	0.01
	Private schools students	2.18	2.03	100		

(A high score in the adjustment test indicates unsatisfactory adjustment, while a low score indicates excellent adjustment.)

The table no. 4 it is shows that, the ashram schools students mean value is 3.38 and standard deviation value is 2.18. Like the private schools students mean value is 2.52 and standard deviation value is 2.03. The ashram schools students mean value is more than private schools students.

Obtained 't' value of the difference between the mean of these two groups was found to be 3.75. This is significant at 0.01 levels. So the null hypothesis was rejected. That is, there was a significant difference of emotional adjustment in ashram schools and private schools students.

Conclusion:

There is significant difference of overall adjustment and three areas in educational, social & emotional adjustment in ashram schools and private schools students. This means, the overall adjustment and educational, social and emotional adjustment of private schools students is higher than that of ashram schools students.

Suggestions:

- 1) A large number of samples can be taken in future research.
- 2) The study area for further research will come from a wide area.
- 3) Various techniques should be used to analyze the scores.

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